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Assessment of Validity and Reliability of Geography Interest Questionnaire among Pre-service Teachers in Colleges of Education, North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed validity and reliability of geography interest questionnaire among pre-service teachers in colleges of education, North-West, Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design. The questionnaire consists of adapted items underwent validation tests for face, content, construct validities and reliability. From the 9 validators' assessments face and content indices found are 0.91 and 0.99 respectively. For construct validity and reliability, the instrument was administered on 129 geography pre-service teachers. The instrument was adapted from a work of Knekta, Rowland, Corwin and Eddy (2020). For construct validity exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were used. The instrument went through EFA, and findings include three-factor structure formed as factor loads related to FGC items are between .802 and .916, those of VGC factor are between .763 and .913, and those of IGA factor are between .860 and .918, all factor loadings exceeded .50, and no cross-loading as well, these indicate convergent and discriminant validity. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) further supported the validity, with composite reliability (CR) (i.e. IGA= 0.908, FGC= 0.925 and VGC= 0.924) and average variance extracted (AVE) (i.e. 0.713, 0.675 and 0.670) are higher than .70 and .50 respectively. And the inter-factor correlation (i.e. 0.244, -0.123, and 0.002) is less than the \sqrt{AVE} (i.e. 0.844, 0.822 and .819). The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is .813. It is proved the instrument is highly valid and reliable, so, it is recommended to use the questionnaire to gather data of geography students' interest in the discipline.

Keyword: Geography, Interest-Questionnaire, Validity and Reliability

Introduction

Teacher education plays a critical role in preparing future instructors to deliver quality instruction and foster a love for learning among students. Among the many factors influencing teaching effectiveness is the interest of students in the subject they are trained to teach. Geography is a combination of sciences and social sciences that studies man, manish activities, places and the physical environment including both living and nonliving things (Dempsey, 2023). In geography, sub disciplines like physical geography represents science, Geographic Information System (GIS) is an application of technology, geography land survey is a part of civil engineering, human geography includes arts and social sciences, and geodesy is a part of mathematics. Geography education complements science in studies of the biophysical environment by studying a wider scope of relationships and interactions and by combining scientific knowledge with contributions from the social sciences (Pallathadka & Pallathadka, 2021). Geography education is crucial for societal security, economic and political development, it prepares students for various careers related to geography and contributes to global literacy (Hagge, 2023; Huh & Jo, 2023; Mathews, DeChano-Cook & Bloom, 2023). Teaching geography is very important because the discipline has high priority for the development of individual, community, nation and the world in various aspects (Keller, 2019). Geography academic performance can be influenced by such factors as individuals' desire to learn geography related content for effective geography teaching and learning process.

Interest is a persistent desire to reengage over time as well as a psychological condition of attention and passion toward a specific subject (Holmes, 2018). Interest describes a person's generally long-lasting psychological desire to repeatedly engage with particular classes of objects (Ofem & Domike, 2022). Academic performance depends on interest, which is a powerful motivating factor that drives learning, directs academic and professional paths and energizes learning (Quinlan & Renninger, 2022). Interest is a motivator that affects learning and performance, teachers should concentrate on how they can best promote

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the development of their students' interest (Wild, 2022). Interest can play a significant role in learning as the pre-service teachers are more likely to invest time and effort in activities or topics of their interest.

Geography pre-service teachers are typically enrolled in geography teacher education programs, which can include formal academic courses, practical teaching experiences and pedagogical training, in order to become a qualified geography teacher (Ammoneit, Turek & Peter, 2022). During pre-service phase, individuals learn about educational theories, teaching methodologies, classroom management, curriculum development, assessment strategies, Geography subject content and other essential aspects of teaching (Lee, 2019). The pre-service teachers have unique personal characteristics, experiences and preferences into the classroom, which shape their interest and engagement with geography. Even when resources are adequate and teaching methods are effective, these individual differences can influence how they perceive, respond to and ultimately develop an affinity for the subject.

This study aimed to assess validity and reliability of geography interest questionnaire among pre-service teachers in colleges of education, North-West, Nigeria. By assessing its validity and reliability, the study focused on ensuring the tool accurately captures pre-service teachers' interest, which is crucial for designing effective interventions to enhance motivation and teaching quality. Furthermore, the study aligns with the broader goals of improving geography education by understanding the attitudinal and motivational factors influencing pre-service teachers.

Statement of the Research Problem

Despite the importance of pre-service teachers' interest in shaping their future teaching practices, there is a lack of widely validated instruments specifically designed to measure this interest in geography (i.e. using face, content & construct validities, and reliability on the other hand). Existing instruments often lack specificity or fail to capture the multidimensional nature of interest, including Feelings toward geography-related content (FGC), Value that geography contents hold for individual (VGC), and Involvement in geography-related activities (IGA) (Ajayi, Agamber & Angura, 2017; Boukayoua, Kaddari & Bennis, 2021; Elsner et al, 2022). Without a valid and reliable questionnaire, stakeholders such as teachers, curriculum designers, and policymakers may struggle to identify areas needing attention or intervention most. Consequently, this gap hinders efforts to enhance teacher training programs and ensure the effective teaching of geography. The challenge, therefore, lies in developing an instrument that not only measures interest but also meets the psychometric standards of validity and reliability. This study addresses this critical gap by rigorously assessing the PTIGQ to ensure its applicability and accuracy in capturing the interest of pre-service teachers in geography.

Objectives of the study:

1. To assess validity of Geography interest questionnaire among pre-service teachers in colleges of Education in North-west, Nigeria.
2. To determine the construct validity of the questionnaire using exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses.
3. To evaluate the reliability of the questionnaire through measures of internal consistency (i.e. Cronbach's alpha reliability).

Research Questions:

1. What is the validity of Geography interest questionnaire among pre-service teachers in colleges of Education in North-west, Nigeria?
2. What are the key components of pre-service teachers' interest in geography that the questionnaire aims to measure?
3. What is the reliability of the questionnaire in measuring pre-service teachers' interest in geography?

Hypotheses:

1. The questionnaire will not demonstrate strong face and content validities, as determined by expert reviews.
2. The construct validity of the questionnaire will not be confirmed, by alignment between exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses results.
3. The questionnaire will not exhibit high internal consistency (i.e. Cronbach's alpha ≥ 0.7) reliability.

Methodology

The research design is descriptive survey which involves gathering of data by studying a representative sample of the entire group (Creswell, 2018). Survey research was considered appropriate for the study because the study involved the entire geography pre-service teachers' interest in the discipline, in which the representative sample of 129 pre-service teachers extracted from the population responded to the questionnaire. Before administering the instrument to the pre-service teachers, the instrument was validated by 9 experts. The experts' assessments was computed using Cohen's Kappa index to test the face and content validity indices. Pre-Service Teachers' Interest in Geography Questionnaire (PTIGQ) has two sections, section A involves demographic information of the pre-service teacher and section B consists the items of pre-service teacher interest in Geography adapted from the work of (Knekta, Rowland, Corwin & Eddy, 2020). It is a close-ended questionnaire, designed to

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be answered by geography pre-service teacher, with such rating scale as: Always (AL) stands for 5, often (OF) stands for 4, sometimes (ST) stands for 3, rarely (RA) stands for 2 and never (NE) stands for 1. Initially the data collected is ordinal type, after the transformation process as rated above, before main analysis on the computer system the data transformed into interval type. Eventually the questionnaire provided interval.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the validity of Geography interest questionnaire among pre-service teachers in colleges of Education in North-west, Nigeria?

Hypothesis 1

The questionnaire will not demonstrate strong face and content validities, as determined by expert reviews.

Face Validity

Face validity was conducted to ensure that the research instrument is clear and easy to understand, and to identify, correct or eliminate any ambiguous or misleading items. Based on the expert assessment rate, the face validity index (FVI) was computed using Cohen’s Kappa index for face validity, which is regarded as proportion. The face validity index (FVI) was computed by $FVI = SRA/NR$ (Yusoff, 2019a; Desai & Patel, 2020).

Table 1: Validators’ Rates in Percentage and FVI Computation

S/N	Validators	Rates in Percentage	FVI
1	A	100	$FVI = \frac{SRA}{NR} = \frac{821}{9}$
2	B	100	
3	C	88	
4	D	99	$FVI = 91.2$
5	E	74	$\therefore FVI = 91\%$
6	F	86	
7	G	85	
8	H	91	
9	I	98	
	SRA	821	

Table 1 shows the percentage of the validators’ rates yielded 91% [Kappa value = 0.91, $p = .000 < .005$], which is the accepted value (Roy, Sukumar, Philip, & Gopalakrishna, 2023). Furthermore, Desai and Patel (2020) emphasized a percentage (%) of rates less than 80 is poor and requires restructure, 80–90 is substantial and requires some amendment, and 90–100 is full, that is, to be retained. For this study, 91% fall within 90–100, which is full.

Content Validity

Content validity was assessed to ensure whether the instrument adequately covers all the relevant content areas and avoid omitting important aspects of the concept. The validators rated content validity of each item of the questionnaire. Based on the expert assessment rate, the Item-level Content Validity-Index (I-CVI) was computed using Cohen’s Kappa index for face validity, which is regarded as proportion. The Item-level Content Validity-Index (I-CVI) was computed by $I-CVI = SRA/NR$ (Roy, Sukumar, Philip & Gopalakrishna, 2023; Yusoff, 2019b; Gilbert & Prion, 2016). The percentage of the validators’ rates yielded 99% [Kappa value = 0.99, $p = .000 < .005$], which is the accepted value. Roy, Sukumar, Philip & Gopalakrishna (2023) stressed that a percentage of rates less than 0.7 = needs elimination, 0.7–0.79 = needs revision and higher than 0.79 = appropriate, therefore, the 99% index is appropriate and accepted.

Research Question 2

What are the key components of pre-service teachers' interest in geography that the questionnaire aims to measure?

Hypothesis 2

The construct validity of the questionnaire will not be confirmed, by alignment between exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses results.

Construct Validity

Initially KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity were used to ensure the suitability of the data for factor analyses. The KMO is .800 and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity ($\chi^2 = 2180.161$, $df = 136$, $P = .001$), which indicate the 129 sample size

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is adequate, and can be used for the factor analyses (i.e. EFA and CFA). Since the KMO value is greater than .60 and the Bartlett's Test result is statistically significant, the data is appropriate for factor analysis (Ateş & Altuner Çoban, 2022).

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Factorization and rotation methods were used to discover the factor construct in which Principal Component Analysis and Promax Rotation were used. As a result of this, 13 items (FGC_7, FGC_8, FGC_9, VGC_1, VGC_8, IGA_6, IGA_7, IGA_8, IGA_9, IGA_10, IGA_11, IGA_12 and IGA_13) out of the 30 items loaded on a factor different from their counterpart were removed, to ensure no cross-loading and no low-loading. The remaining 17 items were re-running and the three-factor structure was formed.

Table 2: Factor Load Values of the Interest in Geography Construct

Factor	Items	Factor load values		
		1	2	3
Feelings toward geography-related (FGC)	FGC_1	Working with the subject matter and problems of geography is among my favorite activities.	.837	
	FGC_2	After a long weekend or vacation I look forward to getting back to my geography classes.	.850	
	FGC_3	Being involved in geography classes puts me in a good mood.	.826	
	FGC_4	I chose to study geography primarily because of the interesting subject matter involved.	.883	
	FGC_5	I generally have fun when I am learning geography topics.	.916	
	FGC_6	I like reading about geography.	.802	
	VGC_2	I really see value in the things that I am learning in geography.		.763
Value that geography contents hold for individual (VGC)	VGC_3	Studying geography has a lot to do with whom I want to become as a person.		.882
	VGC_4	Compared to other things that are important to me (e.g., hobbies and social life), learning about geography is of greater importance.		.913
	VGC_5	Learning about geography is more important to me than leisure and amusement.		.897
	VGC_6	I am certain that studying geography has a positive influence on my personality.		.886
	VGC_7	I am confident that learning about geography directly corresponds with my personal preferences.		.864
Involvement in geography-related activities (IGA)	IGA_1	I discuss outside of class what I am learning in my in geography classes.		.867
	IGA_2	I talk about things that I learned in geography rather than my hobbies.		.894
	IGA_3	In my free time and unrelated to my coursework, I read magazines, articles or books related to the topics of geography.		.918
	IGA_4	If I had enough time, I would work more intensively with certain aspects of geography, even if they had nothing to do with any course requirements.		.907
	IGA_5	Even before coming to college, I voluntarily spent time thinking about topics in geography.		.860

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations

The factor loads of the first factor related to the items are between .802 and .916, those of the second factor are between .763 and .913, and those of the third factor are between .860 and .918, as shown in table 2. With factor load value above .30 provides the criteria for an item to be included within a factor, so, there is no low-loading as all the factor load values are above .50, this means that all the items converge. Also there is no cross-loading, as no item load on more than one factor, this means

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there is no discriminant validity. These findings revealed that the construct validity of the items is provided (Hair, Risher, Sarstedt & Ringle, 2019).

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) involve utilization of the maximum likelihood method to confirm the three-factor structure produced by the exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Figure 1 shows the factor distributions and values obtained from the CFA.

Fig. 1 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) Structure

After the EFA, the standardized regression weights and correlation values in the AMOS output were used to compute the convergent and discriminant validity, which was done in the Excel package. The Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) provide the convergent validity, the CR condition of satisfaction or benchmark is 0.7, while for the AVE values is 0.5. For discriminant validity, the square root of the AVE such as (\sqrt{AVE}) value is compared with the inter-factor correlation. The inter-factor correlation should be less than the square root of the AVE. Table 7 provides the CR, AVE, \sqrt{AVE} , and inter-factor correlation values for the convergent and discriminant validity of the interest in geography items.

Table 3: CR, AVE, \sqrt{AVE} and Inter-Factor Correlation of Interest in Geography Construct

Factor	CR	AVE	IGA	FGC	VGC
IGA	0.908	0.713	0.844		
FGC	0.925	0.675	0.244	0.822	
VGC	0.924	0.670	-0.123	0.002	0.819

As the CR values (i.e. 0.908, 0.925 and 0.924) are above .70 and AVE values (i.e. 0.713, 0.675 and 0.670) are above .50 as shown in the Table 3, so the convergent validity is achieved. The inter-factor correlation (i.e. 0.244, -0.123, and 0.002) is less than the square root of the AVE (i.e. 0.844, 0.822 and .819), so the discriminant validity is achieved. As the convergent and discriminant validities are attained it can be inferred that the construct validity achievement has been confirmed.

Research Question 3

What is the reliability of the questionnaire in measuring pre-service teachers' interest in geography?

Hypothesis 3

The questionnaire will not exhibit high internal consistency (i.e. Cronbach's alpha ≥ 0.7) reliability.

Reliability

Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients were computed for each individual factor and for all items of the questionnaire collectively to check the internal consistency of the scale.

Table 4: Cronbach's Alpha Values of PTIGQ Scale and its Factors

S/N	Factor	Number of Items	Alpha Value
1	FGC	6	.925
2	IGA	5	.934

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3	VGC	6	.935
PTIGQ		17	.813

Table 4 displays the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients found for each factors is high (i.e. FGC 0.925, IGA 0.934 and VGC 0.935) and for all items of the questionnaire collectively is 0.813 (Ateş & Altuner Çoban, 2022; Adeniran, 2019). This revealed that the questionnaire has high reliability.

Summary of Findings

In summary, the questionnaire has high reliabilities and reliability in support with such findings as:

1. Face validity of the questionnaire is 91% and fall within 90–100, which is full. And content validity of 99% index, which is also appropriate.
2. The findings also revealed the achievement of construct validity using EFA and confirmed by using CFA.
3. And finally the questionnaire is reliable at 0.813.

Discussion of Findings

This study sought to provide a scientifically validated and reliable instrument that contributes to understanding and improving teacher education in geography. Therefore the main goal of the study was to validate the adapted Pre-Service Teachers' Interest in Geography Questionnaire (PTIGQ). The PTIGQ was adapted and went through validation processes to ensure its reliability and validity. Validation procedures included face, content and construct validity assessments. For construct validity and reliability, the instrument was administered on 129 geography pre-service teachers, with 13 items rejected due to errors in completion. Missing values were addressed using the "mean of nearby points" method in the SPSS package. The face and content validity index (FVI) was found to be 0.91 or 91%, and Item-level Content Validity-Index (I-CVI) was found to be 0.99 or 99%, meeting the acceptable range. However, the items were adapted from original sources without face and content validity assessments.

The instrument items were adapted from a study of Knekta, Rowland, Corwin and Eddy (2020), the main aim of the study was to create an instrument to measure undergraduate biology students' interest. A total of 348 participants involved in the factor analyses. While the current study made certain modifications and subtractions of items from 30 to 17 most representative of the items, to ensure no cross-loading and no low-loading factor items. The instrument went through EFA indicating convergent and discriminant validity. The CFA confirmed the structure, yielding high CR and AVE values, while the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is 0.813, affirming validity and reliability of the instrument.

Conclusion

From the study findings and the results obtained it is proved that the instrument is highly valid and reliable, and the application of the Questionnaire is supported. This instrument can be adopted by researchers, lecturers and teachers for evaluating interest in geography of targeted students. Other education researchers could be encouraged to adapt and gather validity evidence for the instrument and apply it in their different disciplines. This effort can foster a comprehensive understanding of students' interest across disciplines and facilitate the creation of a knowledge base supporting students' persistence in education.

Recommendations

As a result of the research findings some recommendations were made as follows:

1. Since the questionnaire demonstrates excellent face validity (91%) and content validity (99%), future efforts should ensure the same rigorous standards in designing and validating similar instruments. This includes the involvement of not only subject matter experts, but from various relevant disciplines, such as, English language, educational psychology, measurement and evaluation, and including a sample from the targeted participants, to evaluate the relevance and clarity of questionnaire items and performing comprehensive content reviews to maintain appropriateness across different contexts.
2. With construct validity successfully achieved through Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and confirmed by Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), the questionnaire is proven to measure the intended constructs effectively. It is recommended to apply this validated instrument to broader contexts, such as assessing pre-service teachers' interest in geography across different educational institutions or regions, to gather more comprehensive data for comparative analysis.

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- Utilize the Reliable Questionnaire in Longitudinal Studies: With a reliability score of 0.813, the questionnaire is consistent and dependable for measuring pre-service teachers' interest in geography. It is recommended to use this tool for longitudinal studies to track changes in interest levels over time and to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions designed to enhance engagement in geography education.

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References:

- Adeniran, A. O. (2019). Application of Likert Scale's Type and Cronbach's Alpha Analysis in an Airport Perception Study. *Scholar Journal of Applied Sciences and Research*, 2(4), 01-05. <https://innovationinfo.org/articles/SJASR/SJASR-4-223.pdf>
- Ajayi, V. O., Agamber, T. and Angura, T. (2017). Effect of Gender on Students' Interest in Standard Mixture Separation Techniques Using Ethnochemistry Teaching Approach. *Sky Journal of Educational Research*, 5(5), 27-33. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3066324>
- Ammoneit, R., Turek, A. and Peter, C. (2022). Pre-Service Geography Teachers' Professional Competencies in Education for Sustainable Development. *Education Science*, 12(42) 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12010042>.
- Ateş, S. & Altuner Çoban, G Ş (2022). A Validity and Reliability Study on Developing a Scale for Assessing Classroom Teachers' Attitudes Towards Illustrated Children's Books. *Educational Policy Analysis and Strategic Research*, 17(3), 222-237. <https://doi.org/10.29329/epasr.2022.461.11>
- Boukayoua, Z., Kaddari, F. and Bennis, N. (2021). Students' interest in science learning and measurement practices. Questions for research in the Moroccan school context. *SHS Web of Conferences* 119, article 05006. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202111905006>.
- Creswell, J. W. (2018). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (5th ed.). Pearson.
- Desai, S. & Patel, N. (2020). ABC of Face Validity for Questionnaire. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, 65(1), 164-168. <http://dx.doi.org/10.47583/ijpsrr.2020.v65i01.025>
- Dempsey, C. (2023). *What is Geography?* <https://www.geographyrealm.com/definition-geography/>
- Elsner, J. N., Sadler, T. D., Zangori, L., Friedrichsen, P. J. and Ke, L. (2022). Student interest, concerns, and information-seeking behaviors related to COVID-19. *Disciplinary and Interdisciplinary Science Education Research*, 4(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43031-022-00053-2>
- Gilbert, G. E. and Prion, S. (2016). Making Sense of Methods and Measurement: Lawshe's Content Validity Index. *Clinical Simulation in Nursing*, 12(12), 530-531. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cens.2016.08.002>
- Hagge, P. D. (2023). Find It on a Map: Country Location Identification in a University Geography Classroom, 2016–2022. *Journal of Geography*, 122(5), 105-114. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221341.2023.2224374>
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J.J., Sarstedt, M. and Ringle, C.M. (2019) When to Use and How to Report the Results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31, 2-24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203>
- Holmes, A. G. (2018). The Role of Interest and Enjoyment in Determining Students' Approach to Learning. *Educational Process: International Journal*, 7(2), 140-150. <http://dx.doi.org/10.22521/edupij.2018.72.4>.
- Huh, S. and Jo, I. (2023). Successes and Struggles: Evaluating Geospatial Technologies Integration in Geography Lessons using TPACK. *Journal of Geography*, 122(5), 126-139. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221341.2023.2224814>.
- Keller, K. H. (2019). The current state of geography education in the United States. *The Geography Teacher*, 16(4), 148–149. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19338341.2019.1663747>
- Knekta, E., Rowland, A. A., Corwin, L. A., and Eddy, S. (2020). Measuring university students' interest in biology: Evaluation of an instrument targeting Hidi and Renninger's individual interest. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 7(1), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-020-00217-4>.
- Lee, D. (2019): Cultivating pre-service geography teachers' awareness of geography using story Maps. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education*, 44(3), 387-405. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03098265.2019.1700487>.

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- Mathews, A. J., DeChano-Cook, L. M. and Bloom, C. (2023). Enhancing Middle School Learning about Geography and Topographic Maps Using Hands-on Play and Geospatial Technologies. *Journal of Geography*, 122(5), 115-125. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221341.2023.2226156>.
- Ofem U. A. and Domike, G. (2022). Pupils Learning Preferences and Interest Development in learning. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(21), 31-38. www.iiste.org
- Quinlan, K. M. and Renninger, K. A. (2022). Rethinking employability: how students build on interest in a subject to plan a career. *Higher Education* 84(1), 863–883. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-021-00804-6>
- Roy, R., Sukumar, G.M., Philip, M. & Gopalakrishna, G. (2023). Face, content, criterion and construct validity assessment of a newly developed tool to assess and classify work related stress (TAWS– 16). *PLoS ONE* 18(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0280189>
- Wild, S. (2022). Trajectories of subject-interests development and influence factors in higher education. *Current Psychology: A Journal for Diverse Perspectives on Diverse Psychological Issues*, 1(42), 12879–12895. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-02691-7>
- Yusoff, M.S.B. (2019a). ABC of response process validation and face validity index calculation. *Education in Medicine Journal*, 11(3), 55–61. <https://doi.org/10.21315/eimj2019.11.3.6>
- Yusoff, M.S.B. (2019b). ABC of content validation and content validity index calculation. *Education in Medicine Journal*, 11(2), 49–54. <https://doi.org/10.21315/eimj2019.11.2.6>